

INFLUENCE OF GEOMETRICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WOOL FIBERS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Annotation

The article presents the results of a study of the degree of influence of the fineness and length of wool fibers on the mechanical properties of the fibers.

Keywords

Wool, sorting, classification, fineness, length, breaking load

Most important indicator at sorting wool is index average diameter fibers (fineness), which is main criterion assessment of its spinning ability and is used in setting prices. Correct organization sorting and classification local woolen fiber, which depends from quality measuring processes and accuracy of the measuring instruments used will further ensure rational usage of raw materials, stable flow technological processes spinning, weaving and finishing, which ensures the production of competitive products. In connection with this situation, scientific research aimed at development and implementation of recommendations when compiling the percentage of components of the blend composition of a mixture of wool fibers for the production of high-quality competitive wool or wool blend yarn.

Solving these problems is possible only if you have the most detailed and objective data on the quality indicators of wool. A detailed and comprehensive study of the physical, mechanical and technological properties of wool is of great importance for clarifying and adjusting the optimal technological regimes for the rational use of this valuable raw material, which is also an urgent task.

The length and thickness of the fibers affects the properties of the yarn produced from it. The strength and thickness of the product depends on the thickness of the threads. Thinner yarn is more uneven in its properties; when carded, it becomes more tangled, forming knots and lumps, which spoils the quality and appearance.

Wool fineness is one of the main results of selection and breeding work and a key characteristic for a particular breed, which determines the importance of its study when planning work to improve the productive qualities of animals.

Objects of research: samples of wool from merino sheep breeds were selected in accordance with the requirements of the standard GOST 20576-88 - Natural sorted wool. Acceptance rules and sampling methods.

The test results are shown in tables 1-2.

Table 1 -Qualitative characteristics of wool fibers

p/p	Breed name (color)	Length, mm	Standard deviation in fineness	Class	CV, %	Linear density, mtex
1	Merino (cream)	46-56	19.16	64 ^k	3.9	0.413
2	Merino (beige)	89.96	20.6	60 ^k	3.6	0.442
3	Merino (white)	60-65	21.5	58 ^k	4.4	0.529

To study and predict the influence of the properties of wool fibers on the quality characteristics of wool and wool blend yarn, the mechanical characteristics of wool fibers were determined, given in Table 2.

Table 2 - Mechanical characteristics of wool fibers

Fineness, microns	20.6	22.05	26.4
Breaking load, sN	8.7	9.3	10.6
Absolute error, km	21.5	20.9	20.6

To study the significance of the influence of geometric parameters on the mechanical characteristics of wool fibers, multiple regression analysis was

carried out.

Regression equation (regression equation estimate)

$$Y = 1.6856 + 0.00347X_1 + 0.3207X_2, (1)$$

Interpretation of regression coefficients. The constant evaluates the aggregated influence of other (except for x_i taken into account in the model) factors on the result Y and means that Y in the absence of x_i would be 1.6856. The coefficient b_1 indicates that as x_1 increases by 1, Y increases by 0.00347. The coefficient b_2 indicates that as x_2 increases by 1, Y increases by 0.3207. The partial correlation coefficient differs from the simple linear pair correlation coefficient in that it measures the pairwise correlation of the corresponding characteristics (y and x_i) provided that the influence of other factors (x_j) on them is eliminated.

The closeness of the joint influence of factors on the result is assessed by the multiple correlation index. Unlike the pairwise correlation coefficient, which can take negative values, it takes values between 0 and 1. Therefore, R cannot be used to interpret the direction of a relationship. The closer the actual values of y_i are located relative to the regression line, the smaller the residual dispersion and, therefore, the larger the value of $R_{y(x_1, \dots, x_m)}$. Thus, with an R value close to 1, the regression equation better describes the actual data and factors have a stronger influence on the result. With an R value close to 0, the regression equation poorly describes the actual data and the factors have little impact on the result.

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{s_e^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{0}{1.89}} = 1 \quad (2)$$

Multiple correlation coefficient

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{0}{1}} = 1 \quad (3)$$

We obtain a similar result when using other formulas:

$$R = \sqrt{1 - (1 - r_{yx1}^2) \cdot (1 - r_{yx2|x1}^2)} \quad (4)$$

$$R = \sqrt{1 - (1 - 0.0822^2) \cdot (1 - 1^2)} = 1 \quad (5)$$

The relationship between trait Y and factors X_i is very strong. We will calculate the correlation coefficient using the known values of linear pair correlation coefficients and β -coefficients.

$$R = \sqrt{\sum r_{yxi} \beta_{yxi}} = \sqrt{r_{yx1} \beta_{yx1} + r_{yx2} \beta_{yx2}} \quad (6)$$

$$R = \sqrt{0.0822 \cdot 0.0714 + 0.997 \cdot 0.997} = \sqrt{1} = 1 \quad (7)$$

The closer this coefficient is to one, the more the regression equation explains the behavior of Y. New explanatory variables are added to the model as long as the adjusted coefficient of determination increases.

Conclusions:

As a result of the calculations, a multiple regression equation was obtained:

$$Y = 1.6856 + 0.00347X_1 + 0.3207X_2 \quad (8)$$

An economic interpretation of the model parameters is possible: an increase in X_1 by 1 unit leads to an increase in Y on average by 0.00347 units; increase in X_2 by 1 unit leads to an increase in Y on average by 0.321 units. Based on the maximum coefficient $\beta_2 = 0.997$, we conclude that the factor X_2 has the greatest influence on the result Y. The statistical significance of the equation was tested using the coefficient of determination and Fisher's test. It was established that in the situation under study, 100% of the total variability of Y is explained by changes in factors X_j . It was also found that the model parameters are statistically significant. The factor X_2 ($r = 0.9974$) has the greatest influence on the effective attribute, which means that when building the model it will be the first to enter the regression equation.

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